

Genetic Algorithm Tuned PID Controller for Rotor Position Control of BLDC Motor

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Abstract: In this paper rotor position of the BLDC motor controlled using PID controller. The Proportional gain (KP), Integral gain (KI), Derivative gain (Kd) of the PID controller are tuned using evolutionary algorithms. Since, classical controllers PID are failing to control the drive when weight parameters are also changed. The main aim of this paper is to analyze the implementation of Genetic Algorithm (GA) for optimize PID controllers parameters for rotor position control of BLDC motor with three objective function integral of absolute error (IAE), mean squared error (MSE) and IAE+MSE. The genetic algorithm were implemented and analyzed on a second order plant model of a BLDC motor with the aim of developing a rotor position controller. The results obtained from GA algorithms were compared with considered objective functions. It was found that the Genetic Algorithm with objective IAE+MSE outperformed other considered objective functions.

Key words: BLDC motor • PID controller • Genetic algorithm (GA) • IAE • MSE

INTRODUCTION

BLDC motor has been generally utilized as a part of industry even in spite of the fact that its upkeep expenses are higher than the prompting motor. Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) controllers have been generally utilized for speed and position control of BLDC motor. The paper accomplishment is to outline a control agenda utilizing Genetic Algorithm with considering of non linearity powerful of the framework. Hereditary Algorithm or in short GA is a stochastic calculation taking into account standards of regular determination and Hereditary qualities. The Genetic Algorithms (GAs) are a stochastic worldwide hunt technique that impersonates the procedure of regular development. Utilizing hereditary calculations to perform the tuning of the controller will bring about the ideal. The change of incredible torque execution the motor drives is exceptionally key in created and amassing used and other reason applications, for instance, electric trains steel moving manufacturing plants and, modified controllers [1]. Purpose of this paper is to control the rotor position of BLDC motor for the reason that BLDC motor has been by and large used as a piece of

monetarily regardless of the way that its bolster costs are higher than various motor. Generally, a broad torque execution the BLDC motor drive must have dominating component rotor position control taking after and load variable to perform undertaking. The BLDC motor drives, as a consequence of their straightforwardness, effortlessness of use, high commitment, extraordinary cost and adaptabilities have for quite a while been a spine of collecting applications and private contraptions where position control and speed control of motor are required. The BLDC motor drives are frequently less significant for mainly force rating. In the blink of an eye days, Rotor position control of BLDC motor has pulled in amazing investigate and different procedures have progressed. For rotor position control of BLDC motor, for the most part utilized controllers are traditional PID [2]. Commonly, the BLDC motor drive systems have indeterminate and nonlinear sort which worsen execution of controllers. In perspective of these reasons Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controllers have been viably used as a piece of control applications since 1950 and are the for the most part often used mechanical controllers today [3]. PID controllers spread

different important sorts. It gives info. As PD improves Transient response (i.e. it have the ability to expect the movements in the midst of subordinate action) and PI improves execution of predictable state response (i.e. reduce continuing state equalization in the midst of major action or law), blend of two may be used to propel general time response of the structure. Despite this, PID controllers have outstandingly uncomplicated control structure and are less costly [4]. The objective of this paper is to examine the execution of Genetic Algorithm (GA) for perfect tuning of PID controllers parameters and number their purposes of enthusiasm over the common tuning system Genetic Algorithms (GA) are flexible heuristic request considering transformative considerations of ordinary decision and innate qualities. Innate Algorithms are capable and astute choices under the most ideal conditions course of action among the speed of each achievable game plan. The Genetic Algorithms were used to survey the perfect PID controller expansion values where execution files, IAE were used as the objective limits. It was tentatively established that the Integral of Absolute Magnitude of the error (IAE) execution foundation delivers the best PID controller when contrasted and other execution paradigm. The proposed procedures were confirmed utilizing a second request physical model of plant as BLDC motor where tuning calculations were driven for the most part by the obtained framework information and the coveted execution parameters determined by the client are effectively fulfilled. Resultant upgrades on the stride reaction conduct of BLDC motor rotor position control framework are appeared for two cases. This paper is organized as follows: system modeling of BLDC motor is displayed in Section 2, PID controller brief describe in section 3, bief prologue to genetic algorithm is talked about in Section 4, last two Section 5 and 6 individually describe simulation result and conclusion of this paper rotor position control of BLDC motor.

Modeling of Brushless DC Motor: The BLDC motor drive system through voltage control and the voltage apply to stator of the motor is controlled thus by control the speed and rotor position of the motor. Typical inverter system for a BLDC motor and the other related equations for obtaining the mathematical model are taken from [18, 19]. The BLDC motor is connected to the output of the inverter as shown in Figure.1. The inverter input terminals are connected to constant supply voltage. It is assumed that there are no power losses in the inverter and the motor winding is connected in star.

Fig. 1: Typical inverter system for a BLDC motor.

For a symmetrical winding of motor and assuming balanced supply system, the voltage equation across the motor winding is expressed as,

$$V_a = R_a i_a + L_a \frac{di_a}{dt} + M_{ab} \frac{di_b}{dt} + M_{ac} \frac{di_c}{dt} + e_a \tag{1}$$

$$V_b = R_b i_b + L_b \frac{di_b}{dt} + M_{ba} \frac{di_a}{dt} + M_{bc} \frac{di_c}{dt} + e_b \tag{2}$$

$$V_c = R_c i_c + L_c \frac{di_c}{dt} + M_{ca} \frac{di_a}{dt} + M_{cb} \frac{di_b}{dt} + e_c \tag{3}$$

where V_a, V_b and V_c denotes phase voltage of the motor. R_a, R_b and R_c represents stator winding resistances. Phase current of the motor are represented by i_a, i_b and i_c . Self inductance of the motor winding is represented by L_a, L_b and L_c and the mutual inductances between stator windings are denoted by $M_{ab}, M_{ac}, M_{ba}, M_{bc}, M_{ca}$ and M_{cb} respectively.

The back-EMF waveforms e_a, e_b and e_c are the functions of angular velocity of the rotor shaft, so

$$e = k_e * \omega_m \tag{4}$$

where K_e is the back-emf constant.

Considering the above equation, the BLDC motor mathematical model can be represented by the following equation in matrix form,

$$\begin{bmatrix} L_a & M_{ab} & M_{ac} \\ M_{ba} & L_b & M_{bc} \\ M_{ca} & M_{cb} & L_c \end{bmatrix} \frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ i_c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} V_a \\ V_b \\ V_c \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} R_a & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & R_b & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & R_c \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ i_c \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} e_a \\ e_b \\ e_c \end{bmatrix} \tag{5}$$

Fig. 2: Rotor position control scheme of BLDC motor

If is assumed that the rotor has a surface-mounted design, which is generally the case for today’s BLDC motors. Also there is no saliency such that the stator self inductances are independent of the rotor positions and hence,

$$L_a = L_b = L_c = L$$

And the mutual inductances will have the form as given below,

$$M_{ab} = M_{ac} = M_{ba} = M_{bc} = M_{ca} = M_{cb} = M$$

Assuming three phase balanced system, all the phase resistances are equal. Therefore,

$$R_a = R_b = R_c = R$$

Rearranging the equation (5) after incorporating the above assumption yields,

$$\begin{bmatrix} L & M & M \\ M & L & M \\ M & M & L \end{bmatrix} \frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ i_c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} V_a \\ V_b \\ V_c \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} R & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & R & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & R \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ i_c \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} e_a \\ e_b \\ e_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The electromechanical torque is expressed as

$$T_{em} = J \frac{d\omega_r}{dt} + B\omega_r + T_L \quad (7)$$

where J , B and ω_r are denotes the moment of inertia, frictional coefficient and angular velocity of the motor respectively. T_L is the load torque.

Since the electromagnetic torque of 3-phase BLDC motor is dependent on the current, speed and back-EMF waveforms, the equation for instantaneous electromagnetic torque (7) can be modified and represented as,

$$T_{em} = \frac{1}{\omega_m} (e_a i_a + e_b i_b + e_c i_c) \quad (8)$$

The rotor position control scheme of BLDC motor is shown in Figure 2. The control structure consists of two loops, namely, inner loop and outer loop. An inner loop is used for synchronizing the inverting gate signal with back electromotive force or rotor position of the motor. The outer loop is used to sense the actual rotor position of the rotor using rotor position encoder. The actual rotor position is compared with the reference rotor position; thereby error (e) and rate of change of error ($\dot{A}e$) are obtained. Error and rate of change of error are processed by the rotor position controller and provides a control signal (U_m) to the switching logic circuit. The switching logic circuit provides the necessary pulse width modulated (PWM) signal of the inverter gate with respect to rotor position of the motor and the control signal output obtained from the controller.

PID Controller: PID controllers have been generally utilized for control system. The most basic stride for applying the PID controller is the tuning of its parameters.

Table 1: Effects of Increasing the PID Controller Parameters

Parameter	Rise Time	Overshoot	Settling time	Steady state error
K_p	Decrease	Increase	Small change	Decrease
K_i	Decrease	Increase	Increase	Reduce
K_d	Small change	Decrease	Decrease	Small change

The tuning handle needs a considerable measure of time and exertion. In the most pessimistic scenario, the terrible tuning prompts a poor execution of the controlled system. PID Controller is an essential control circle of input component and is generally utilized as a part of control framework. The different side effects of a the BLDC motor, for example, dissemination and creation can debase the execution of customary controllers [6]. PID Controllers utilize three essential sorts of parameter or modes: Proportional (P), Integral (I) and Derivative (D). While corresponding and vital control is utilized as single control approach, a subordinate control utilized is that it enhances the transient response of the system. In this paper it is executed a strategy to control the rotor position of BLDC motor which above is appeared in Figure 2. in Figure.2. The rotor position error between the references and actual rotor position and the genuine rate is given as data to a PID controller. The PID controller taking a shot at the adjustments in error its productiveness, to control the procedure data such that the blunder is diminishes. Tuning of PID give complete data about the suspicion and controllers [7]. The objective of the tuning procedure is to decide the PID controller parameters that fulfill the execution details of the controlled framework, for example, the rising time, the most extreme overshoot, the settling time and the consistent state blunder. Be that as it may, it is hard to acquire the alluring estimations of these necessities at the same time. As appeared in Table I, for instance, bigger estimations of relative addition results in quicker reaction while overshoot is expanded. Hence, an ideal tuning method is of extraordinary significance. PID Controller is a major control circle of feedback instrument and is comprehensively used as a piece of control system.

The unique symptoms of the BLDC motor, for instance, scattering and development can degenerate the execution of standard controllers [8]. PID Controllers use three essential sorts of parameter or modes: Proportional (P), Integral (I) and Derivative (D). PID controller as appeared in shown in Fig. 3. The PID controller taking a shot at the changes in mix-up its productiveness, to control the methodology information such that the goof is reduces. PID controller is generally called the three-term of guideline controller parameter, whose trade limit is routinely made in the parallel structure given by correlation (9) or the ideal structure is given by numerical explanation (9) [9]. An undertaking PID controller is otherwise called the three-term of primary controller parameter, whose exchange capacity is ordinarily composed in the parallel structure given by comparison (11) or the perfect structure is given by mathematical statement (9).

General form of the Transfer function of a PID controller is given as,

$$G(S) = K_p + K_i \frac{1}{s} + K_d S \tag{9}$$

$$G(S) = K_p \frac{K_i}{s} + K_d S = \frac{K_d s^2 + K_p s + K_i}{s} \tag{10}$$

$$G(s) = K_p \left(1 + \frac{1}{T_i s} + T_d s \right) \tag{11}$$

where e = Error signal
 K_p = Proportional Constant
 K_i = Integral Constant
 K_d = Derivative Constant

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int_0^t e(t) dt + K_d \frac{de(t)}{dt} \tag{12}$$

Genetic Algorithm: The genetic algorithm is a technique for explaining both compelled and unconstrained enhancement issues that depends on normal choice [10]. genetic algorithms fit in with the bigger class of evolutionary algorithms (EA), which generate solutions to

Fig. 3: PID Controller with System

Fig. 4: Flowchart of GA for PID tuning

optimization problems using techniques inspired by natural evolution, such as inheritance, mutation, selection and crossover [11]. The GAs were initially proposed by John Holland in 1970 [12]. As a way to discover great answers for issues that were generally computationally unmanageable. Holland's composition hypothesis, this hypothesis is likewise called the basic hypothesis of hereditary calculations, is broadly taken to be the establishment for clarifications of the force of hereditary calculations. It says that short, low request schemata with above-normal wellness increment exponentially in progressive eras [9-16]. In this paper, GA is utilized to decide the ideal estimations of the PID controller parameters that fulfill the required element execution qualities of the BLDC motor drive framework. Fig. 4 demonstrates the steps of procedure GA based tuning of

PID controller parameters. In the primary, GA is introduced. At that point, it makes a starting populace of PID controller parameters. The populace is created haphazardly, covering the whole scope of conceivable arrangements. The populace is made out of chromosomes. Every chromosome is a competitor answer for the issue. The chromosome structure consists of three parameters (K_p , K_i and K_d) are incorporated. The chromosomes are connected in the BLDC motor drive system and the dynamic execution attributes of the system are resolved for every chromosome. At that point, the wellness esteem for every chromosome is assessed utilizing the goal capacity. In light of the wellness estimations of the original, a gathering of best chromosomes is chosen to make the following populace. After choice, hybrid and change are connected to this surviving populace so as to

enhance the following generation [13]. The procedure proceeds until the end standard is accomplished or the quantity of eras is come to its greatest worth. Hereditary calculation is likewise talked about in part 3 the stream graph of GA is appeared in Figure 4. Creating the beginning populace is the initial step of GAs. The populace is made out of the chromosomes that are parallel piece string. The relating assessment of a populace is known as the (wellness work) the wellness quality is greater and the execution is better [14-17]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fitness function is the key to use the GA [14]. The most essential stride in applying GA tuning strategy is to pick the target work that is utilized to assess the fitness value of every chromosome. In this paper, two objective functions are utilized and their execution is looked at. The first depends on integral of the absolute error (IAE) index, the second depends on mean of the squared error (MSE) index and these papers in objective function additionally plan through the MATLAB coding. The parameters of GAs in this study are set as in Table II. The GA advancement process based IAE index and MSE index are appeared in Fig. 5, Fig.6 and Fig.7 individually. For every case, the PID controller parameters are resolved. The objective function is given as:

$$IAE = \int_0^T |e(t)| dt \tag{13}$$

$$MSE = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T e(t)^2 dt \tag{14}$$

$$IAE + MSE = \int_0^T |e(t)| dt + \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T e(t)^2 dt \tag{15}$$

Genetic algorithm is run for 100 trails to optimize the parameter of the PID controller with three objective functions. Final optimum parameter for the PID controller is shown in Table III.

Table II: Settings of Ga Parameters Values

Parameter	Value
Lower bound [Kp Ki Kd]	[0 0 0]
Upper bound [Kp Ki Kd]	[2 2 2]
Populations	25
Generations	100
Ranges of PID parameters	0-2
Crossover fraction	0.8
Mutation rate	0.01
Elite count	5
Trial	100

Table III: Parameter of the PID controller optimized using Genetic Algorithm

Objective function	PID parameter			Fitness
	K _p	K _i	K _d	
IAE	1.4229	0.024086	0.28832	2.06109
MSE	1.6616	0.028481	0.37751	0.11093
IAE+MSE	1.8729	0.016553	0.302	1.86297

Fig. 5: GA optimization progression based objective function (IAE) index

Fig. 6: GA optimization progression based objective function (MSE) index

Fig. 7: GA optimization progression based objective function (IAE+MSE) index

Fig. 8: Simulink model of the rotor position controlled BLDC motor.

Fig. 9: Rotor position of the BLDC motor for step input reference.

Fig. 10: Rotor position of the BLDC motor for ramp input reference.

The simulink model of the rotor position controlled BLDC motor is shown in Fig. 8. In order to verify the developed controller of the BLDC motor is subjected to two different operating conditions such as step input and ramp input reference command. Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 shows the rotor position response of the BLDC motor with step and ramp input reference. From the Fig.9, PID optimized with objective function IAE+MSE has superior tracking response then other objective function. Rotor position of the BLDC motor settle quickly and no overshoot in the output response of the BLDC motor. From the Fig. 10, PID optimized with objective function IAE+MSE has enhanced performance in terms of rise time, settling time and overshoot and undershoot.

CONCLUSIONS

The paper has presented, genetic algorithm tuning of the PID controller for rotor position control of BLDC motor. The genetic algorithm technique optimizes the parameter of the PID controller led to a satisfactory close loop response for the system under consideration. Objective of this developed algorithm for optimize the PID parameters through the genetic algorithm based on different objective function. From the results, objective function IAE+MSE has superior performance in terms of minimum rise time, minimum settling time, less overshoot, less undershoot and nearly zero steady state error. The simulation results show that more improved performance using objective function IAE+MSE as compared to objective functions IAE and MSE.

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